

DOCTORAL DISSERTATIONS IN EDUCATION

IN INDIA 2005-2008: A STUDY

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Introduction

The modern concept of education demands that we modify or change out right the curriculum. Many of the traditional subjects which aimed at training the mind and preparation for college entrance are either easing out of the curriculum. An attempt at enrichment and preparation for vacations and leisure have brought many contributions such as public school, music, art, dramatics, health, physical education, family relationships, home management, cooking, sewing, manual training and many others.

There is today a distinct tendency to break down subject matter and to organize units of study around present-day problems or interests of the children. It is held that more subject matter will be used by this process and those skills, abilities; understanding and appreciations would even more effectively be accomplished by virtue of the interest children feel in pursuing their own goals.

In education however, is to be afforded by a series of experiences these experiences must be organized in some way to indicate their contributions to development; to facilitate learning retention skills and to show relation of one experience to others and eventually to a unified whole. The teacher sets the stage and remains in the background in such a learning situation. Through this process there is more learning and less teaching; more study and activity and less recitation. Pupils are guided in the solution of vital problems of individual and social life.

The school environment contributes largely to the development of personality. Physically the environment should be comfortable, attractive, and free from strain and menaces to health. Mentally it should be stimulating, satisfying and interesting. Socially it should provide for working together on tasks that are mutually interesting a sharing

experience. And emotionally the school should be free from fear, harsh discipline excessive noise and excitement and too much emphasis given to competition. There must be pupil teacher rapport for only through this happy and constructive relationship can there be spontaneity and creativeness.

The research studies are carried out mainly in the education in India particularly those in the universities and various institutions. Taking consideration of the Ph.D. works conducted in India universities, it is desired to know the trend of research conducted in education. The paper is designed to reflect the Ph.D. works in education in India during a period of eight years from 2005-2008.

Objectives of study

The study aims at the following objectives

- 1 To find out year wise education research.
- 2 To know the area wise distribution of research works in education.
- 3 To identify the contribution of universities and various institutions in awarding doctoral degrees.

Scope and Limitations

The study covers research in education at the Ph.D. Level only accepted for doctoral degree by Indian universities. The study does not consider the research works in education registered in universities the period of coverage is from 2005-2008 a period of four years. It has considered only those titles of doctoral theses appeared in the University News published these appeared by Association of Indian Universities (AIU)

Methodology

As stated earlier, the main source of data/information collected is from University News periodically lists out the doctoral theses accepted by different universities in India. These doctoral dissertations have been listed out and analysis has been made. The year wise distribution of area during the study period has also been made. All the 893 doctoral dissertations awarded during the period of four years by Indian Universities have been considered for the study. These were grouped according to different categories. Distribution

has also been made for universities awarding the number of theses. Different institution wise also been made to identify the growth pattern of research work.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

Table. No.1 Yearwise Distribution of Theses Awarded

Sr. No.	Year	No. of Theses Awarded
1	2005	166
2	2006	207
3	2007	305
4	2008	216
Total		893

The Table No.1 represents the yearwise distribution of theses which shows that the highest numbers of theses, i.e.305 were awarded in the year 2007, while lowest numbers of 166 theses were awarded in the year 2005. Total number of 893 theses in education has been produced during the four years period.

Table No.2 Faculty wise No. of Theses Awarded

Sr. No.	Faculty	No. of Theses Awarded
1	Education	800
2	Physical Education	93
	Total	893

The Table No.2 represents the faculty wise distribution of theses. Total number of 800 theses in education has been produced during the four years period. Total number of 93 theses in physical education has been produced during the four years period.

Table No.3 Distribution of Theses across Subjects

Sr. No.	Subjects	No. of Theses Awarded
1	Educational Psychology	393
2	Educational Philosophy	07
3	Educational Technology	78
4	Development of Curriculum	17
5	Teacher Education	52
6	Teaching Learning Process	253
	Total	800

In order to determine the education research in various subjects categories, the analysis has been made in Table -2 Taking consideration of research works in education ; six (6) subjects been categorized. It is found the subject Educational Psychology have the highest number of three hundred and ninety three (393) doctoral dissertations awarded. A total of two hundred and fifty three (253) theses have been produced during the period in teaching learning process. A total of seventy eight (78) theses have been produced during the period in Educational Technology process. . A total of fifty two (52) theses have been produced during the period in Teacher Education process. A total of seventeen (17) theses have been produced during the period in Development of curriculum process. . A total of seven (7) theses have been produced during the period in Educational Philosophy. A total of ninety three (93) theses have been produced during the period in physical education.

Table No. 4 Distribution of Theses Awarded by Universities

Sr. No.	University	No. of Theses Produced
1	Osmania University Hederabad	22
2	Vardaman Mahaveer Open Uni. Kota	11
3	Shivaji Uni. Kolhapur	17
4	Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada Uni. Aurangabad	39
5	North Eastern Hill Uni. Shillong	26
6	Nagaland Uni. Kohima	01
7	North Gujarat Uni. Patan	10
8	Rajiv Gandhi Uni. Itanagar	05
9	Himachal Pradesh Uni. Shimla	15
10	Maharaja Sayajirao Uni. Of Baroda Vadodara	09
11	Banglore Uni. Banglore	24
12	Panjab Uni. Chandigarh	75
13	Banaras Hindu Uni. Varanasi	19
14	Karnatak Uni. Dharwad	32
15	Rani Durgawati Vishwavidyalaya, Jabalpur	05
16	Sambalpur Uni., Sambalpur	01
17	Uni. Of Kashmir Srinagar	05

18	Andra Uni. Waltair	25
19	Assam Uni. Silchar	02
20	Kurukshetra Uni. Kurukshetra	46
21	Maharshi Dayanand Uni. Rohtak	25
22	North Maharashtra Uni. Jalgaon	20
23	Mizoram Uni. Aizawl	03
24	Swami Ramanandteerth Marathwada Uni. Nanded	15
25	Guru Nanak Dev. Uni. Amritsar	02
26	Sambalpur Uni. Burla	06
27	Utkal Uni. Bhubaneswar	59
28	Dibrugarh Uni. Dibrugarh	02
29	Nagpur Uni. Nagpur	14
30	Devi Ahilya Vishwarvidyalaya Indore	17
31	Lucknow Uni. Lucknow	17
32	South Gujrat Uni. Surat	08
33	Aligarh Muslim Uni. Aligarh	10
34	Ani. Uni. Chennai	06
35	Rashtriya Sanskrit Vidyapeeth Tirupati	12
36	Gulberga Uni. Gulberga	11
37	Jiwaji Uni. Gwalior	04
38	Arunachal Uni. Itanagar	03
39	Y. C. M. O. Uni. Nasik	26

40	Uni. Of Burdwan, Burdwan	01
41	Jamia Milia Islamia Uni. New Delhi	17
42	Madhya Pradesh Bhoj (open) Uni. Bhopal	05
43	Acharya Nagarjuna Uni. Nagarjunnagar	03
44	Uni. Of Jammu, Jammu	02
45	Gandhigram Rural Ins. Gandhigram	04
46	Babasabeb Bhimrao Ambedkar Bihar Uni. Muzaffarpur	01
47	Uni. of Lucknow , Lucknow	02
48	Nagaland Uni. Kohima	02
49	Kuvempu Uni. Shankarghatta	05
50	Vikram Uni., Ujjain	01
51	Guru Ghasidas Uni. Bilaspur	02
52	Mahatma Phule Rohilkhand Uni. Bareilly	17
53	Gour Vishwavidyalaya Sagar	04
54	Panjab Uni. Patiala	05
55	Uni. Of Mumbai	01
56	Jawaharlal Nehru. Uni. New Delhi	09
57	Uni. Of Delhi	01
58	Sardar Patel Uni. Vallabh Vidyanagar	01
59	Dibrugarh Uni. Dibrugarh	02
60	Barkatullah Uni., Bhopal	03
61	Saurashtra Uni. Rajkot	19

62	Manonmaniam Sundarnagar Uni. Tirunelveli	05
63	Mohanlal Sukhadia Uni. Udaipur	17
64	Bundelkhand Uni. Jhansi	08
65	Chhatrapati Shahuji Maharaj Uni. Kanpur	40
66	Guru Jambheshwari Uni. Of Sci. and Tech. Hisar	03
67	Andhra Uni. Vishakhapatnam	12
68	Sant Gadge Baba Amravati Uni. Amravati	08
69	Sambalpur Uni., Jyoti Vihar, Bhubaneswar	01
70	Uni. Of Kashmir Shrinagar	01
71	Rajiv Gandhi Uni. Rono Hills, Itanagar	01
72	Manipur Uni., Imphal	04
73	Gorakhpur Uni., Gorakhpur	04
74	Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia Avadh Uni. Faizabad	04
75	Kannada Uni. Humpi	01
76	Uni. of Calcutta, Kolkatta	08
77	Dr. P. D. Krishi Vidyapeeth. Akola	01
78	Bhavnagar Uni. Bhavnagar	09
79	Fakir Mohan Uni. Balasore	01
80	Deen Dayal Upadhyaya	01
81	Guru Nanak Dev. Uni. Amritsar	02
Total		880

In order to ascertain the contribution of universities in India awarding doctoral dissertations in education over the period on analysis has been made in Table No.4. All the 81 universities in India have awarded Ph. D. on education during the period. While the Panjab Uni. Chandigarh has highest number of research work. i. e. seventy Five (75) awarded to their scholars. Only one (1) thesis has been produced in Nagaland Uni. Kohima, Sambalpur Uni., Sambalpur, Uni. Of Burdwan, Burdwan, Babasabeb Bhimrao Ambedkar Bihar Uni. Muzaffarpur, Vikram Uni., Ujjain, Uni. Of Mumbai, Uni. Of Delhi, Sardar Patel Uni. Vallabh Vidyanagar, Sambalpur Uni., Jyoti Vihar, Burk, Uni. Of Kashmir Shrinagar, Rajiv Gandhi Uni. Rono Hills, Itanagar, Kannada Uni. Humpi, Dr. P. D. Krishi Vidyapeeth. Akola, Fakir Mohan Uni. Balasore, Deen Dayal Upadhyaya.

Table No. 5 Distribution of Thesis Awarded By Different Institutions

Sr. No.	Institutions	No. of Theses Produced
1	Tata Institute of social Sciences Mumbai	01
2	Avinashilingam Institute of Home sci. and Higher education for women, Coimbatore	03
3	Dayallagh education Institute, Agra	02
4	Zakir Husen centre for educational studies New Delhi	01
5	Not Mentioned	06
	Total	13

In order to ascertain the contribution of different institutions in India awarding doctoral dissertations in education over the period an analysis has been made in Table No.5 One thesis have been produced in TISS Mumbai. Three theses has been produced in Avinashilingam Institute of Home sci. and Higher education for women, Coimbatore. Two theses has been produced in Dayallagh education Institute, Agra. One thesis has been produced in Zakir Husen centre for educational studies New Delhi. Six theses have been not mentioned in universities or institutions.

Table No.6 Guide ship Pattern of research works

Sr. No.	Guide ship	No. of Research works
1	Single	666
2	Joint	31
3	Not-mentioned	96
Total		893

In order to determine the Guide ship pattern of Ph.D. scholars, the above table shows that six hundred sixty six (66) Ph.D. scholars have been guided by single persons. Thirty one (31) scholars have been chosen jointly by guide ship for their research works. In ninety six (96) cases, no mention of guide has been made in TableNo.6

Conclusion

The present paper has undertaken to trace the development of education research at doctoral level for the four years period. i.e. 2005-2008 . It is identified that the highest of these i.e. that the highest numbers of theses, i.e.305 has been produced in the year 2007, while lowest numbers of 166 theses has been produced in the year 2005.Educational Psychology subject to be the only broad subject area which has been attracted the attention of education. The universities in the state of Panjab University Chandigarh have awarded highest number of Ph.D. In respect to guide-ship pattern, maximum number of scholars has chosen to opt single guides-ship to conduct their research.

Suggestions for further research

- 1) The study may be repeated comparing with two countries.
- 2) A comparative research may be undertaken to study the effectiveness of education in different universities in Maharashtra.

Recommendations

- 1) To study the research e-learning in various industries.
- 2) In 21st century Information Technology education exists in all faculties.

References

1. University News, Association of India Universities, New Delhi. All issues from 2005-2008

